

A final peer reviewed article has now been published:

Corbisier P, Petrillo M, Marchini A, Querci M, Buttinger G, Bekliz M, Spiess K, Polacek C, Fomsgaard A, Van den Eede G. **A qualitative RT-PCR assay for the specific identification of the SARS-CoV-2 B.1.1.529 (Omicron) Variant of Concern.** J Clin Virol. 2022;152:105191.

DOI: 10.1016/j.jcv.2022.105191

PMID: 35640400

PMCID: PMC9126828

THE PUBLICATION IS FREELY AVAILABLE AT:

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcv.2022.105191>